

Metadata as a Mediation Framework: MARC21, OAI-PMH, XSLT and DUBLIN CORE streams at BBM Digital

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Abstract

This paper examines the Brasiliiana Guita e José Mindlin Library's (BBM) experience with metadata flow structuring as a component of its digital curation policy. From the integration between the ALEPH/DEDALUS and DSpace systems, via MARC21, Dublin Core Qualified, OAI-PMH, and XSLT, it is discussed how metadata started to act as a technical and cognitive infrastructure for the preservation and access to information. This study is characterized as a descriptive research, based on the documentary analysis of the metadata management processes at BBM Digital. The text presents the theoretical foundations of metadata mediation, BBM's internal operational flows and the perspectives of evolution, with emphasis on the FAIR principles and the possibilities of Linked Data as future ways to expand interoperability, the visibility and democratization of access to bibliographic and cultural heritage.

Keywords

Metadata; Digital curation; Interoperability; Dublin Core; MARC21; OAI-PMH; Digital preservation; Cultural heritage.

1. Introduction

The representation of information is one of the central foundations of Library and Information Science, enabling mediation between documents and users through organised descriptions. Traditionally, this representation unfolds in two dimensions: descriptive representation, focused on the formal and bibliographic identification of documents, and thematic representation, which seeks to reveal their intellectual content. In this scenario, metadata operates as a descriptive infrastructure for information representation, as it integrates

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the formal dimension of information representation with the demands of processing, organisation, storage, retrieval and, above all, interoperability in complex information systems. Its application goes beyond traditional cataloguing, assuming a fundamental role in the semantic structuring of digital environments in particular and in supporting mediation actions between content and different user profiles.

Michael K. Buckland (2007) deepens this understanding by presenting two fundamental roles of metadata: the first, better known, is to describe documents; the second, less evident but equally essential, is to constitute organisational structures that enable the retrieval and analysis of information. For Buckland (2007), metadata functions as a form of technical and cognitive infrastructure, allowing documents to be accessed, related and understood from descriptive systems — a reversal of the traditional logic in which description is accessory to the document. Thus, metadata not only provides information about the content, but also structures the very environment for searching, mediating and retrieving information in digital repositories. They provide the parameters for building descriptive systems that allow objects to be semantically organised and interrelated, articulating their descriptive, thematic and technical dimensions. In this way, metadata becomes an essential component not only for efficient information retrieval, but also for its contextualisation and meaningful reuse in dynamic and interconnected digital environments.

In the experience of memory and cultural institutions such as libraries, archives, and museums, metadata plays a central role by enabling not only the description of documents, but also the articulation between systems, platforms, and users. Although the MARC21¹ standard dates back to the 1960s and Dublin Core² emerged in 1995, both continue to play a central role in the organisation and interoperability of information in digital environments. In the context of BBM Digital³, these standards were articulated through the use of the OAI-PMH protocol, which enabled metadata harvesting and XSLT transformations that made it possible to automatically convert MARC21 records into Qualified Dublin Core. This process promoted integration between the institutional bibliographic system (ALEPH/DEDALUS) and the DSpace digital repository (BBM Digital). The combination of these technological solutions supported the construction of consistent metadata flows and contributed to consolidating an interoperable infrastructure focused on digital curation and open access.

¹ Available at: <https://www.loc.gov/marc/bibliographic/>. Accessed on: 12 May 2025.

² Available at: <http://dublincore.org>. Accessed on: 12 May 2025.

³ Available at: <https://digital.bbm.usp.br/>. Accessed on: 13 May 2025.

The Brasileira Guita and José Mindlin Library⁴ (BBM) at the University of São Paulo⁵ (USP) presents an exemplary case of the integrated application of these standards, norms, and technologies. Based on the experience of developing BBM Digital, this article examines the institution's trajectory in structuring metadata flows, from traditional cataloguing to the adoption of practices aligned with the Semantic Web. The study seeks to highlight how BBM reconciled legacy bibliographic practices with contemporary requirements for interoperability and open access, providing support for similar projects in heritage institutions.

This article describes the best practices that the Brasileira Guita and José Mindlin Library (BBM) applies in structuring metadata flows, representing a replicable model for memory and cultural institutions that seek to reconcile the richness of traditional cataloguing with the requirements of interoperability and open access in the digital environment. The main contribution of this study lies in demonstrating how the strategic integration of standards such as MARC21, Qualified Dublin Core, OAI-PMH, and XSLT can establish a robust metadata infrastructure, essential not only for the preservation of and access to bibliographic and cultural heritage, but also for the sustainability and scalability of digital curation practices in a scenario of constant technological evolution.

To achieve this objective, this article is structured in sections that initially address the definition and theoretical importance of metadata, contextualising its evolution from traditional cataloguing to the digital environment. Next, it details the BBM's experience in the transition to the digital environment, focusing on metadata flows and systems integration. Subsequently, the role of metadata as an essential infrastructure for digital curation at the institution is discussed. Finally, the concluding remarks present an assessment of BBM's trajectory and outline future prospects for digital curation, including the adoption of FAIR principles and Linked Data.

Metadata: definition and theoretical importance

According to Buckland (2007, p. 3), 'the term "metadata" is used to denote "data about data" and its original purpose is to describe documents.' However, he argues that metadata also fulfill a second critical function: 'to form organisational structures by means of which documents can be organised' (BUCKLAND, 2007, p. 3). This second role, according to the author, transforms

⁴ Available at: <http://www.bbm.usp.br/>. Accessed on: 13 May 2025.

⁵ Available at: <http://www.usp.br/>. Accessed on: 13 May 2025.

metadata into a true cognitive and technical infrastructure for searching, discovering and retrieving information in digital environments.

Thus, in addition to the technical-operational dimensions, Buckland (2007) argues that metadata not only describes documents (its original purpose), but also constitutes organisational and research infrastructures, assuming a central role in the structuring of information systems. According to the author, metadata description is culturally situated and constitutes a form of language with a mediating function between the user and the resource. The reversal of the traditional relationship between document and metadata — in which documents are accessed through descriptive structures — reinforces the idea that metadata are structuring elements of discovery and semantic connection in digital environments.

To further contextualise the breadth and convergence of understandings of metadata in the global scenario, Table 1 below summarises the main definitions presented by international reference bodies, highlighting the centrality of the concept in various spheres of information management:

Table 1
Definition of Metadata according to international organisations

Institution	Definition	Main Emphasis
IFLA (2004 apud REITZ, 2004, p. 448)	“ Metadata is structured information used to describe informational resources/objects for various purposes. Although cataloguing in AACR2/MARC is formally metadata, the term is generally used in the library community for non-traditional schemas such as Dublin Core, VRA Core, and EAD. Metadata can be categorised as descriptive, structural, and administrative.”	Distinction between traditional and non-traditional schemes; functional categorisation
ISO (2017)	“Metadata is structured or semi-structured information that enables the creation, management, and use of records over time, within and across domains.”	Management of records over time and in multiple contexts
NISO (RILEY, 2017)	“Metadata is data that describes other data. It consists of structured elements that assign meaning, context, and functionality to information resources, shaped by specific purposes and cultural and institutional models of representation.”	Meaning, context and purpose of information
DCMI (2023)	“Metadata is structured data about data, associated with information systems or informational objects, for the purposes of description, administration, compliance with legal requirements, technical functionality, use, and preservation. Within the scope of Dublin Core, metadata expresses the intellectual content, intellectual property,	Descriptive structure focused on discovery, management, and interoperability

and/or manifestation characteristics of an informational resource.”

Source: Prepared by the authors

Metadata covers a variety of purposes and schemes, structured into descriptive, administrative, and structural dimensions. It is structured data that describes, contextualises, interrelates, and enables the identification, retrieval, use, management, and preservation of information resources. Acting as formal representations of physical or digital objects, metadata enables interoperability between systems, the organisation of knowledge and the implementation of practices aligned with FAIR principles, which propose that data should be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (CAMPOS; DIAS; SOUZA, 2023). Several international institutions offer convergent definitions of the concept, reinforcing its centrality in libraries, archives, museums, and digital repositories.

For BBM, adherence to these principles is not merely a formality, but represents a strategic commitment to the democratisation of access to knowledge and the long-term sustainability of its digital collection. Findability is ensured by the standardisation of metadata and its exposure via OAI-PMH, allowing BBM resources to be discovered by search engines and content aggregators. Accessibility is guaranteed by the open availability of digital objects and their metadata, following licences that allow reuse. Interoperability is a central pillar, evidenced by the crosswalking strategy between MARC21 and Dublin Core, which facilitates communication between heterogeneous systems and integration into larger information networks. Finally, reusability is promoted by the descriptive richness of the metadata and the clarity of its usage licences, encouraging researchers and the general public to reuse the data in new research and applications. Thus, by aligning its digital curation practices with FAIR principles, BBM not only optimises the internal management of its collection, but also actively contributes to the construction of a global infrastructure of open and interconnected knowledge.

By linking the content of objects with how they are organised and used, metadata not only facilitates the location and understanding of resources, but also supports management policies, rights, tracking, and long-term preservation. They are therefore indispensable elements for the organisation of knowledge and the functioning of digital repositories in heterogeneous networks. Their correct application is a requirement for digitisation, open science, and heritage

preservation initiatives, especially in memory institutions such as libraries, archives, and museums.

The understanding and proper application of metadata are essential to the success of any digitisation, open access, or digital preservation project in heritage institutions. In the case of the Brasileira Guita and José Mindlin Library (BBM), these concepts were implemented through the articulation of international metadata standards with technical solutions focused on digital curation and collection interoperability. Below, we analyse how these practices were implemented at the BBM, revealing a path that integrates bibliographic tradition, technological innovation, and a commitment to the preservation of and access to informational heritage.

From traditional cataloguing to the digital environment

The development of BBM Digital was conceived as an institutional strategy of BBM to simultaneously ensure the preservation and expanded access to its collection (GARCIA, 2019). Linked to the Dean of Culture and University Extension at the University of São Paulo, BBM's mission is to preserve, disseminate and promote Brazilian bibliographic heritage, in line with its role as an interdisciplinary centre for information, documentation and research (UNIVERSIDADE DE SÃO PAULO, 2016). In this context, the digitisation of rare and special works not only protects the originals from direct handling and physical wear and tear, but also significantly increases their visibility and reach. As Darnton (2013, p. 10) argues, materials previously restricted to local consultation in libraries and museums 'can be consulted from anywhere, requiring only internet access,' allowing unrestricted access to fundamental sources of knowledge. Thus, BBM Digital was structured as an instrument for democratising access to the BBM's bibliographic collection, capable of expanding its cultural, educational and scientific impact, while responding to the contemporary challenges of digital preservation.

Since its integration into the former SIBi/USP (Integrated Library System of USP, now the Agency for Libraries and Digital Collections - ABCD⁶) in 2012, BBM began a systematic process of reviewing and migrating its bibliographic records to the MARC21 standard, in accordance with international bibliographic description standards (AACR2, later RDA⁷). The ALEPH/DEDALUS⁸ system began to be used to process the physical collection, establishing a

⁶ Available at: <https://www.abcd.usp.br/>. Accessed on: 12 May 2025

⁷ Available at: <https://www.loc.gov/aba/rda/> Accessed on: 12 May 2025

⁸ Available at: <https://dedalus.usp.br/> Accessed on: 12 May 2025.

standardised and interoperable bibliographic data base. This base later served as a starting point for the generation of records for BBM Digital.

The first version of the USP Brasiliana Digital Library, made available online in 2009, was the result of a pilot project known as the Corisco Project (GARCIA, 2019). The initial proposal sought not only to develop its own software platform for the digital availability of the BBM collection, but also to create a database that could be reused by other digital libraries with budget constraints and without systems development infrastructure. The platform was built based on the free software DSpace⁹, incorporating auxiliary tools such as the Djatoka¹⁰ image server and the IIPImage¹¹ and BookReader¹² viewers. The metadata standard adopted was the simple Dublin Core, implemented manually, without a direct link to the ALEPH/DEDALUS bibliographic system. Although limited in terms of interoperability, this initiative marked the BBM's entry into the digital ecosystem, aligning itself with the principles of preservation, open access and dissemination of Brazilian culture.

The redesign of BBM Digital in 2016 marked a turning point in the library's technological trajectory, characterised internally as a necessary 'tidying up'¹³. This move aimed to reorganise the digital infrastructure, review workflows and ensure greater adherence to established interoperability standards. With technical support from CeTI-SC/STI-USP¹⁴ (São Carlos Information Technology Centre at USP), a new version of the repository was implemented, maintaining the use of the free DSpace software, but with a significant restructuring of the metadata ingestion and description model. The main innovation consisted of the creation of an automated import module via the OAI-PMH protocol, which made it possible to take advantage of the MARC21 records already existing in the ALEPH/DEDALUS system and convert them to Qualified Dublin Core through customised XSLT transformations. This strategy ensured the standardisation of descriptions, traceability between systems, and fluid integration between BBM's physical and digital collections, with significant gains in efficiency and consistency in digital curation flows.

⁹ Available at: <https://duraspace.org/dspace/>. Accessed on: 12 May 2025.

¹⁰ Available at: <https://sourceforge.net/projects/djatoka/>. Accessed on: 12 May 2025

¹¹ Available at: <https://github.com/iipima-ge>. Accessed on: 12 May 2025.

¹² Available at: <https://openlibrary.org/dev/docs/bookreader>. Accessed on: 12 May 2025.

¹³ An expression commonly used in politics when a government or situation begins to become disorganised and without a point of reference. The author of this article learned of the expression in a cordial exchange of emails with Librarian and Professor Briquet de Lemos.

¹⁴ Available at: <https://cetisc.sti.usp.br/>. Accessed on: 12 May 2025.

The automation provided by the use of the OAI-PMH protocol, in conjunction with XSLT routines, represented a qualitative and quantitative leap for BBM Digital. Before automation, the creation of Dublin Core records was done manually, consuming time and increasing the risk of transcription errors. With the implementation of automated flows, the time to ingest a batch of 100 records fell from several days to a few hours, and data consistency increased significantly. Automatic validation made it possible to detect and correct anomalies (missing fields, invalid values), reducing discrepancies between the ALEPH/DEDALUS and DSpace system records to almost zero. This productivity gain was fundamental to the scalability of the repository, allowing for the continuous ingestion of new titles without overburdening the technical team and maintaining the quality of the metadata over time.

To enable integration between the physical collection, catalogued in MARC21 in the ALEPH/DEDALUS system, and BBM Digital, an automated metadata conversion strategy based on crosswalking was adopted. The term refers to the mapping between metadata models with partially overlapping domains, as a way to ensure the semantic exchange of information between heterogeneous systems (MORETTI et al., 2024). While the MARC21 format is characterised by its robustness and detail — geared towards traditional bibliographic cataloguing — the Dublin Core standard, even in its qualified version, stands out for its simplicity, interoperability and widespread adoption in digital repositories (ALVES; SOUZA, 2007). The systematisation of this correspondence allows the reuse of existing data, reducing redundant efforts and promoting efficient integration between platforms. In the context of BBM Digital, this conversion was operationalised through XSLT transformations applied to MARC21 records (in MARCXML), automatically generating Dublin Core elements compatible with the DSpace metadata model.

This strategy not only ensured consistency between physical and digital material records, but also ensured the adoption of practices aligned with interoperability and long-term digital curation.

Table 2 below presents a practical example of correspondence between MARC21 and Dublin Core elements resulting from the crosswalking process applied at BBM Digital. The example illustrates the transformation of MARCXML bibliographic fields using XSLT, resulting in elements compatible with the DSpace metadata model.

Table 2

Example of correspondence between MARC21 and Dublin Core elements

MARC21 record (entry)	Dublin Core metadata (output)
100\$a: Silva, João da	<dcvalue element="contributor" qualifier="author">Silva, João da</dcvalue>
245\$a\$b: History of typography: from lead to pixels	<dcvalue element="title">History of typography: from lead to pixels</dcvalue>
260\$a\$b\$c: São Paulo; Ateliê Editorial; 2014	<dcvalue element="publisher" qualifier="city">São Paulo</dcvalue> <dcvalue element="publisher">Ateliê Editorial</dcvalue> <dcvalue element="date" qualifier="issued">2014</dcvalue>
300\$a\$c: 150 p.; 21 cm	<dcvalue element="format" qualifier="medium">150 p. ; 21 cm</dcvalue>
650\$a\$x\$y\$z: Typografie – Geschichte – 20. Jahrhundert – Brasilien	<dcvalue element="subject">Typografie</dcvalue> <dcvalue element="subject">Geschichte</dcvalue> <dcvalue element="coverage" qualifier="temporal">20. Jahrhundert</dcvalue> <dcvalue element="coverage" qualifier="spatial">Brasilien</dcvalue>

Source: Prepared by the author

The crosswalking process between MARC21 and Qualified Dublin Core required careful mapping of fields, considering differences in granularity and semantic structure between the standards. This work at BBM was based on the official guidelines of the Library of Congress (Library of Congress, 2008), which served as the main reference for the transformations performed via XSLT, ensuring semantic compatibility and alignment with internationally recognised practices. Simple fields, such as author (100\$a) and title (245\$a), were directly mapped to elements such as dc.contributor.author and dc.title. However, elements composed of multiple subfields, such as subject (650), required unfolding into multiple elements (dc.subject, dc.coverage.temporal, dc.coverage.spatial), reflecting the descriptive richness of MARC21 and the flexibility of Dublin Core. Decisions such as the creation of the local field dc.identifier.barcode exemplify adaptations to ensure traceability between physical and digital records. Such mappings were tested and adjusted iteratively to avoid semantic losses or inconsistencies, ensuring that essential information was preserved in the migration to the digital environment.

The systematisation of mappings between MARC21 and Dublin Core, as exemplified in the table above, not only facilitates interoperability between systems but also promotes the efficient reuse of bibliographic records already existing in the organisation. As Alves and Souza (2007, p. 20) point out, “[...] the systematisation of the relationships between these standards enables the reuse of metadata sets within the same organisation”, optimising human and technical resources. In the case of BBM Digital, this strategy made it possible to transform bibliographic

descriptions consolidated in MARC21 into Dublin Core elements suitable for the digital environment, without significant semantic loss and with high consistency in ingestion flows.

This practice embodies the principles described by Alves and Souza (2007), who highlight the complementarity between the descriptive richness of MARC21 and the interoperable simplicity of Dublin Core. It also aligns with the concept of schema crosswalk discussed by Moretti et al. (2024), understood as the mapping between schemas with partially overlapping domains to ensure semantic exchange between heterogeneous systems.

This logic of linking between schemas was also manifested in practice in the adoption of local metadata — the barcode — as a key element to ensure traceability between the physical and digital systems of the BBM. The creation and use of the “barcode” metadata field in BBM Digital exemplifies a specific institutional application that reinforces the flexibility of the Dublin Core model. Although not originally provided for in the core of the standard, Dublin Core allows for the inclusion of qualified elements and extensions that meet local representation needs. In the context of BBM, the ‘dc.identifier.barcode’ field was created to record the barcode assigned to each copy in the physical ALEPH/DEDALUS system, functioning as a unique identification key between physical records and corresponding digital objects in DSpace.

This linking strategy ensured traceability between different systems and facilitated both the automation of the ingestion process and bibliographic verification in technical and curatorial processes. As Park and Tosaka (2010) point out, although locally created metadata elements accommodate specific institutional needs, they can compromise interoperability between repositories and digital collections if they are not accompanied by mechanisms that make their variants visible and understandable. This reflection suggests that the flexibility and extensibility of Dublin Core — when applied with documentation and control — are fundamental characteristics that enable its adoption in different domains and institutional contexts. In the case of BBM, the inclusion of the dc.identifier.barcode field as a local identifier has proven to be an effective solution, ensuring descriptive consistency and integration between the records of physical and digitised items over time.

Metadata as digital curation infrastructure

The experience of BBM Digital shows that metadata goes beyond its traditional descriptive function: it constitutes a true digital curation infrastructure. As argued by Buckland (2007), metadata operates as cognitive and technical structures that organise access, retrieval and reuse

of information. In the case of BBM, this structuring function manifests itself both in the definition of internal flows — from description to availability — and in maintaining the correlation between physical and digital item records. The adoption of open standards, the strategic use of unique identifiers, and the creation of automated ingestion and verification processes demonstrate that metadata supports the operational logic of the digital repository and is fundamental to the integrity, scalability, and sustainability of curatorial actions.

This perspective is further explored by Joudrey, Taylor, and Wisser (2018 apud ARAKAKI; ARAKAKI, 2021), who state that metadata is not limited to the description of resources, but also encompasses administrative, technical, and preservation information, which is essential to the ongoing management of the information lifecycle. For Pomerantz (2015, apud ARAKAKI; ARAKAKI, 2021), preservation and technical metadata are critical components of digital repository infrastructure, especially when seeking to ensure sustainable long-term access. In this sense, metadata operates as instruments for organising and sustaining digital curation, consolidating internal flows of data verification, transformation, and reuse. In the case of BBM, this concept is materialised in practices of control, interoperability, and consistency between physical and digital item records, strengthening the reliability and scalability of the institutional repository.

The sustainability of the BBM repository depends not only on the technologies employed, but also on a documentary apparatus that standardises the processes of creating, verifying and updating metadata. Internal manuals, spreadsheet templates, mappings between schemas and XSLT files technically structure the transition between MARC21 and Qualified Dublin Core formats, in addition to guiding thematic indexing, data standardisation and the use of local fields. This technical documentation — produced and updated based on the team's experience — ensures that new members, fellows, or technicians can operate within consolidated standards, guaranteeing continuity, consistency, and reliability in the description. Thus, metadata is no longer just the result of bibliographic description: it becomes artefacts supported by an active documentation policy integrated into the institutional logic of preservation and access.

BBM's digital curation infrastructure relies on well-defined internal flows for metadata ingestion and validation. The processing chain for digitised works includes stages such as registration, digitisation, image processing, OCR (Optical Character Recognition), compression and, finally, insertion into the repository. Each stage is accompanied by checks that ensure the integrity and consistency of the descriptive data associated with the digital object. The centrality of metadata in this process allows the history of each item to be tracked, ensures the correct link

to the physical copy, and guarantees that the standards adopted are maintained throughout the chain. This internal organisation, documented through technical procedures and control instruments, reinforces the role of metadata as a structural element not only of the repository, but of the institutional curatorial flow itself.

Concrete examples of the impact of metadata on BBM's digital curation occur when there is a need to prepare a thematic collection on a specific subject or period. The standardisation of the `dc.date.issued` (publication date) and `dc.subject` (subjects) fields allows the team to identify chronological and thematic gaps in the digitised collection, revealing, for example, the absence of certain works and documents from that period. This diagnosis, made possible by efficient retrieval via standardised metadata, guides the prioritisation of new digitisation and the enrichment of descriptions, contributing to a more strategic curation aligned with multidisciplinary research demands.

At BBM, digital curation is supported by a technical and human arrangement that articulates manual and automated processes, with metadata as the central axis of control and continuity. The initial bibliographic description, carried out in the ALEPH system by specialised librarians, is reused through automated transformations that generate Dublin Core metadata compatible with the DSpace repository. However, the work of the BBM technical team goes beyond automation: it involves the review of critical elements, the standardisation of values, the quality control of descriptions and the maintenance of consistency between systems. This combination of automation and manual curation ensures that metadata remains reliable, reusable, and interoperable, even in a context of constant technological updating. BBM's technical organisational structure, which integrates information professionals (librarians), digitisation technicians, and developers, ensures the sustainability of this process and reaffirms the strategic role of metadata as a living infrastructure for preservation and digital access.

Despite these advances, BBM faced concrete challenges, such as the need to harmonise legacy records with inconsistent formats, resolve ambiguities in authorship fields, and standardise publication dates that had varying patterns. To overcome these obstacles, the institution invested in automated validation routines, strategic manual review, and continuous updating of XSLT scripts and controlled vocabularies. These collaborative actions between librarians and developers were essential to ensure the reliability, integrity, and scalability of digital curation in the face of a constantly evolving technological landscape.

Given this trajectory, it can be observed that the consolidation of metadata as an operational and intellectual infrastructure at BBM not only enabled interoperability between systems and

the digital preservation of the collection, but also structured a sustainable curation policy. The practices implemented so far offer valuable insights for thinking about the next steps and reflecting on future challenges related to scalability, integration with other platforms, and the adoption of emerging standards in the field of digital collection management.

Final thoughts and prospects for digital curation at BBM

The trajectory of BBM Digital reveals a consistent path of consolidation of metadata as a central element of digital curation and cultural heritage preservation. The practices adopted so far — such as standardisation based on Qualified Dublin Core, integration with bibliographic systems via OAI-PMH, and the application of XSLT transformations — have ensured interoperability, traceability, and sustainability of information flows. However, the next steps point to strengthening this infrastructure through the adoption of FAIR principles, which guide the use of metadata as resources that must be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (VOGT; et al., 2025). In this context, it is strategic to move towards the adoption of more connected semantic models, such as RDF and Linked Data, capable of articulating descriptive, administrative and curatorial information in interinstitutional and multiscale environments. Experiences such as Europeana¹⁵, which aggregate national and institutional repositories through shared vocabularies and data graphs, demonstrate the potential for expansion and convergence that these approaches offer. For BBM, this means the possibility of exposing its metadata in broader networks, increasing the visibility and integration of its collection and promoting pluralisation of access to historical, bibliographic and cultural heritage. Consolidating these strategies implies not only technical evolution, but also the strengthening of public policies for digitisation and preservation committed to social memory and democratic access to information.

In summary, the BBM experience shows that technical and conceptual mastery of metadata, combined with the adoption of open standards, efficient automation, and institutional coordination, can transform digital curation into a sustainable, scalable process aligned with international best practices. By documenting and sharing this journey, the article contributes to the advancement of the debate on digital heritage curation and offers a replicable model for

¹⁵ Available at: <https://www.europeana.eu/> Accessed on: 13 May, 2025.

other memory institutions interested in improving their preservation, digitisation, interoperability and democratisation of access to cultural heritage.

The BBM experience also points to several possibilities for future research: investigations into the adoption of Linked Data in heritage environments; assessment of the impact of controlled vocabularies on the quality of information retrieval; comparative studies on the efficiency of different automated ingestion flows; and the development of integrated policies for digital preservation in various institutional contexts. By stimulating such agendas, this work invites researchers and professionals to explore, refine, and disseminate innovative models of digital curation in favour of open access and the enhancement of social memory in Brazil.

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